

Vision por computador

29 octubre 2021

Deep learning en segmentacion y
deteccion

What do we mean by
'object recognition'?

Is this a street light?
(Verification / classification)

Where are the people? (Detection)

(Identification)

Sky

What's in the scene? (semantic segmentation)

Moun

Trees

Building

Vendors

People

Ground

Object categorization

What type of scene is it?
(Scene categorization)

Outdoor

Marketplace

City

Activity / Event Recognition

Object Recognition

Is it really so hard?

Find the chair in this image

Output of normalized correlation

This is a chair

Object recognition

Is it really so hard?

Find the chair in this image

Pretty much garbage

Simple template matching is not going to make it

A “popular method is that of template matching, by point to point correlation of a model pattern with the image pattern. These techniques are inadequate for three-dimensional scene analysis for many reasons, such as occlusion, changes in viewing angle, and articulation of parts.” Nivatia & Binford, 1977.

How many object categories are there?

~10,000 to 30,000

Challenge: variable viewpoint

Michelangelo 1475-1564

Challenge: variable illumination

image credit: J. Koenderink

from Apple.
(Actual size)

Challenge: scale

Challenge: Occlusion

Challenge: background clutter

Challenge: intra-class variations

Svetlana Lazebnik

PASCAL VOC 2005-2012

20 object classes

22,591 images

Classification: person, motorcycle

Detection

Action: riding bicycle

Segmentation

Everingham, Van Gool, Williams, Winn and Zisserman.
The PASCAL Visual Object Classes (VOC) Challenge. IJCV 2010.

The PASCAL Visual Object Classes Challenge 2009 (VOC2009)

- 20 object categories (aeroplane to TV/monitor)
- Three (+2) challenges:
 - Classification challenge (is there an X in this image?)
 - Detection challenge (draw a box around every X)
 - Segmentation challenge (which class is each pixel?)

Examples

Classification Challenge

- Predict whether at least one object of a given class is present in an image

is there a cat?

Pascal VOC 2007 Average Precision

Pascal VOC 2012 Average Precision

Detection Challenge

- Predict the bounding boxes of all objects of a given class in an image (if any)

True Positives - Person

UoCTTI_LSVM-MDPM

MIZZOU_DEF-HOG-LBP

NECUIUC_CLS-DTCT

False Positives - Person

UoCTTI_LSVM-MDPM

MIZZOU_DEF-HOG-LBP

NECUIUC_CLS-DTCT

Data Sets

- ImageNet
 - Huge, Crowdsourced, Hierarchical, *Iconic* objects
- PASCAL VOC
 - *Not* Crowdsourced, bounding boxes, 20 categories
- SUN Scene Database, Places
 - *Not* Crowdsourced, 397 (or 720) scene categories
- LabelMe (Overlaps with SUN)
 - Sort of Crowdsourced, Segmentations, Open ended
- SUN *Attribute* database (Overlaps with SUN)
 - Crowdsourced, 102 attributes for every scene
- OpenSurfaces
 - Crowdsourced, materials
- Microsoft COCO
 - Crowdsourced, large-scale objects

IMAGENET Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge (ILSVRC) 2010-2012

~~20 object classes~~ — ~~22,591 images~~

1000 object classes

1,431,167 images

<http://image-net.org/challenges/LSVRC/{2010,2011,2012}>

Variety of object classes in ILSVRC

IMAGENET Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge

Year 2010

NEC-UIUC

[Lin CVPR 2011]

Year 2012

SuperVision

[Krizhevsky NIPS 2012]

Year 2014

GoogLeNet

Convolution
Pooling
Softmax
Other

[Szegedy arxiv 2014]

VGG

[Simonyan arxiv 2014]

MSRA

[He arxiv 2014]

COMPUTER VISION TASKS

Classification

CAT

No spatial extent

Semantic Segmentation

GRASS, CAT, TREE, SKY

No objects, just pixels

Object Detection

DOG, DOG, CAT

Multiple Object

Instance Segmentation

DOG, DOG, CAT

This image is CC0 public domain

SEMANTIC SEGMENTATION

Label each pixel in the image with a category label

Don't differentiate instances, only care about pixels

Semantic Segmentation Idea: Sliding Window

Farabet et al, "Learning Hierarchical Features for Scene Labeling," TPAMI 2013

Pinheiro and Collobert, "Recurrent Convolutional Neural Networks for Scene Labeling", ICML 2014

Semantic Segmentation Idea: Fully Convolutional

Design a network as a bunch of convolutional layers to make predictions for pixels all at once!

Semantic Segmentation Idea: Fully Convolutional

Design network as a bunch of convolutional layers, with **downsampling** and **upsampling** inside the network!

Long, Shelhamer, and Darrell, "Fully Convolutional Networks for Semantic Segmentation", CVPR 2015
Noh et al, "Learning Deconvolution Network for Semantic Segmentation", ICCV 2015

Learnable Upsampling: Transpose Convolution

Recall: Normal 3 x 3 convolution, stride 1 pad 1

Recall: Normal 3 x 3 convolution, stride 2 pad 1

3 x 3 transpose convolution, stride 2 pad 1

- Other names:**
- Deconvolution (bad)
 - Upconvolution
 - Fractionally strided convolution
 - Backward strided convolution

Learnable Upsampling: 1D Example

Output contains copies of the filter weighted by the input, summing at where it overlaps in the output

Need to crop one pixel from output to make output exactly 2x input

Convolution as Matrix Multiplication (1D Example)

We can express convolution in terms of a matrix multiplication

$$\vec{x} * \vec{a} = X \vec{a}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} x & y & x & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & x & y & x & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & x & y & x & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & x & y & x \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ a \\ b \\ c \\ d \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} ay + bz \\ ax + by + cz \\ bx + cy + dz \\ cx + dy \end{bmatrix}$$

Example: 1D conv, kernel size=3, stride=1, padding=1

Convolution transpose multiplies by the transpose of the same matrix:

$$\vec{x} *^T \vec{a} = X^T \vec{a}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} x & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ y & x & 0 & 0 \\ z & y & x & 0 \\ 0 & z & y & x \\ 0 & 0 & z & y \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & z \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \\ c \\ d \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} ax \\ ay + bx \\ az + by + cx \\ bz + cy + dx \\ cz + dy \\ dz \end{bmatrix}$$

When stride=1, convolution transpose is just a regular convolution (with different padding rules)

Convolution as Matrix Multiplication (1D Example)

We can express convolution in terms of a matrix multiplication

$$\vec{x} * \vec{a} = X\vec{a}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} x & y & x & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & x & y & x & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ a \\ b \\ c \\ d \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} ay + bz \\ bx + cy + dz \end{bmatrix}$$

Example: 1D conv, kernel size=3, stride=2, padding=1

Convolution transpose multiplies by the transpose of the same matrix:

$$\vec{x} *^T \vec{a} = X^T \vec{a}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} x & 0 \\ y & 0 \\ z & x \\ 0 & y \\ 0 & z \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} ax \\ ay \\ az + bx \\ by \\ bz \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

When stride>1, convolution transpose is no longer a normal convolution!

Semantic Segmentation Idea: Fully Convolutional

Downsampling:
Pooling, strided convolution

Design network as a bunch of convolutional layers, with **downsampling** and **upsampling** inside the network!

Upsampling:
Unpooling or strided transpose convolution

Input:
 $3 \times H \times W$

High-res:
 $D_1 \times H/2 \times W/2$

High-res:
 $D_1 \times H/2 \times W/2$

Predictions:
 $H \times W$

Object Detection

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Object Detection: Single Object

(Classification + Localization)

This image is CC0 public domain

Often pretrained on ImageNet
(Transfer learning)

Vector:
4096

Fully
Connected:
4096 to 1000

Class Scores

Cat: 0.9
Dog: 0.05
Car: 0.01
...

Multitask Loss

Fully
Connected:
4096 to 4

Box
Coordinates
(x, y, w, h)

Correct label:
Cat

Softmax
Loss

+ → Loss

L2 Loss

Correct box:
(x', y', w', h')

Treat localization as a
regression problem!

Object Detection: Multiple Objects

Each image needs a different number of outputs!

CAT: (x, y, w, h) 4 numbers

DOG: (x, y, w, h)
DOG: (x, y, w, h) 16 numbers
CAT: (x, y, w, h)

DUCK: (x, y, w, h) Many
DUCK: (x, y, w, h) numbers!

.....

Object Detection: Multiple Objects

Apply a CNN to many different crops of the image, CNN classifies each crop as object or background

Dog? NO
Cat? YES
Background? NO

Problem: Need to apply CNN to huge number of locations, scales, and aspect ratios, very computationally expensive!

Region Proposals: Selective Search

- Find “blobby” image regions that are likely to contain objects
- Relatively fast to run; e.g. Selective Search gives 2000 region proposals in a few seconds on CPU

Alexe et al, "Measuring the objectness of image windows", TPAMI 2012
Uijlings et al, "Selective Search for Object Recognition", IJCV 2013
Cheng et al, "BING: Binarized normed gradients for objectness estimation at 300fps", CVPR 2014
Zitnick and Dollar, "Edge boxes: Locating object proposals from edges", ECCV 2014

“Slow” R-CNN

Predict “corrections” to the RoI: 4 numbers: (dx, dy, dw, dh)

Problem: Very slow!
Need to do ~2k independent forward passes for each image!

Idea: Process image before cropping!
Swap convolution and cropping!

Girshick et al, “Rich feature hierarchies for accurate object detection and semantic segmentation”, CVPR 2014.
Figure copyright Ross Girshick, 2015; [source](#). Reproduced with permission.

Fast R-CNN

Girshick "Fast R-CNN" ICCV 2015. Figure copyright Ross Girshick 2015. [source](#). Reproduced with permission.

Faster R-CNN:

Make CNN do proposals!

Insert **Region Proposal Network (RPN)** to predict proposals from features

Otherwise same as Fast R-CNN:
Crop features for each proposal,
classify each one

Ren et al, "Faster R-CNN: Towards Real-Time Object Detection with Region Proposal Networks", NIPS 2015
Figure copyright 2015, Ross Girshick; reproduced with permission

Jointly train with 4 losses:

1. RPN classify object / not object
2. RPN regress box coordinates
3. Final classification score (object classes)
4. Final box coordinates

Faster R-CNN:

Make CNN do proposals!

Faster R-CNN is a **Two-stage object detector**

First stage: Run once per image

- Backbone network
- Region proposal network

Second stage: Run once per region

- Crop features: RoI pool / align
- Predict object class
- Prediction bbox offset

Do we really need the second stage?

Single-Stage Object Detectors: YOLO / SSD / RetinaNet

Input image
 $3 \times H \times W$

Divide image into grid
 7×7

Image a set of **base boxes**
centered at each grid cell
Here $B = 3$

Within each grid cell:

- Regress from each of the B base boxes to a final box with 5 numbers: $(dx, dy, dh, dw, \text{confidence})$
- Predict scores for each of C classes (including background as a class)
- Looks a lot like RPN, but category-specific!

Output:

$$7 \times 7 \times (5 * B + C)$$

Object Detection: Lots of variables ...

Backbone

Network

VGG16

ResNet-101

Inception V2

Inception V3

Inception

ResNet

MobileNet

“Meta-Architecture”

Two-stage: Faster R-CNN

Single-stage: YOLO / SSD

Hybrid: R-FCN

Image Size

Region Proposals

...

Takeaways

Faster R-CNN is slower but more accurate

SSD is much faster but not as accurate

Bigger / Deeper backbones work better

Huang et al, “Speed/accuracy trade-offs for modern convolutional object detectors”, CVPR 2017

Zou et al, “Object Detection in 20 Years: A Survey”, arXiv 2019 (today!)

R-FCN: Dai et al, “R-FCN: Object Detection via Region-based Fully Convolutional Networks”, NIPS 2016

Inception-V2: Ioffe and Szegedy, “Batch Normalization: Accelerating Deep Network Training by Reducing Internal Covariate Shift”, ICML 2015

Inception V3: Szegedy et al, “Rethinking the Inception Architecture for Computer Vision”, arXiv 2016

Inception ResNet: Szegedy et al, “Inception-V4, Inception-ResNet and the Impact of Residual Connections on Learning”, arXiv 2016

MobileNet: Howard et al, “Efficient Convolutional Neural Networks for Mobile Vision Applications”, arXiv 2017

Instance Segmentation

Classification

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Instance Segmentation: Mask R-CNN

Mask R-CNN

Mask R-CNN: Example Mask Training Targets

